

**WOMEN LEADERSHIP AND MATERNAL HEALTH SERVICE DELIVERY IN
ADJUMANI DISTRICT, UGANDA**

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Declaration:

I Iyaa Dominic, declare that this thesis is my original work and has not been previously presented by me or any other person to this university or any higher institution of learning for any academic award.

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Dedication:

To my very best friend late Manya Edward, for his support and love, encouragement, I am what I am because of the mark he left in my life, he was there for me in my dearest time of need, like a friend I never had, for this I will be grateful forever. My wife has been an inspiration and my son Samuel who God gave when we both needed him; they are my inspiration I ever had and will have for my academic endeavours.

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List of Acronyms

LC	LOCAL COUNCIL
LG	LOCAL GOVERNEMENT
UNSCR	UNITED NATIONS SOCIAL CULTURAL RIGHTS
UDHR	UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS
OECD	ORGANIZATIONS FOR ECONOMIC CULTURALLY DEVELOPMENT
HIV	HUMAN IMMUNE VIRUS
AIDS	ACQUIRED IMMUNE DEFICIENCY SYNDROME
NDP	NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN
CEDAW	CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST WOMEN
UDHS	UGANDA DOMESTIC HOUSEHOLD SURVEY
SSA	SUB SAHARAN AFRICA
ANC	AFRICA NATIONAL CONGRESS
NGOS	NATIONAL GOVERNEMENT ORGANIZATIONS
CBOS	COMMUNITY BASED ORGANIZATION
MOH	MINISTRY OF HEALTH
PEAP	POVERTY ERADICATION ACTION PLAN
MGLSD	MINISTRY OF GENDER LABOR AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT
DHT	DISTRICT HEALTH TEAM

Abstract

Background: Maternal health issues are major global issues and every ones responsibilities; in most communities, maternal health services delivery are lagging behind and because of this gaps in service delivery we have lost a considerable number of women and child during the process of delivery and after delivery. Many factors account for this death, but key to this occurrence is the issue of leadership in the health sector. Though the health sector workforce is dominated by women who occupy various posts in the health sector, the leadership position is dominated by men in the health sector. This thesis provides an explanation or overview to the role Women Leaders play in enhancing maternal health services in adjumani district. Women in health leadership can cause a positive change in maternal health if given the opportunity and trained according with relevant trainings on leadership in the health sector.

Methodology: a qualitative descriptive research design was used, where in-depth interviews with participants; focus group discussion with service users of maternal health and observation in Adjumani district with health centre III in charges, health workers, district health officials and district officials. An in depth interview was conducted with 16 health in charges and 7 health workers and a total of 7 district officials as key informants was conducted and two focus group discussion conducted in two health centre three facilities one headed by a woman and another headed a man.

Results: The study revealed that women leadership is crucial to the delivering of improved maternal health services in Adjumani. Women leaders are better communicators and pass forth simple messages to service users and the workers at the health and secondly women advocates for the needs of the grass root women in meetings held at the health centres, districts and other organization focusing on women maternal health and thirdly in planning women leaders give priorities to women and children health in their planning processes.

Conclusions: There is inadequacy of women leadership in the health sector in adjumani district, few health centre IIIs are headed by women, these perform better in maternal health service delivery, Maternal health services are lagging behind because little attention is given to the issue of leadership in these health centres, if attentions is directed to leadership and enhancement is initiated, maternal health issues are being addressed in the long run; maternal health problems are solved if health leadership is dealt with properly.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The maternal mortality risk in sub Saharan African Women is 1 in 31-100 higher than women in developed Nations (Hamel G and Heene A, 2008). Women in Developing Nations run 100-200 times the risk of dying in pregnancy and childbirth; the lifetime risk of a woman in a low resource nation of dying in pregnancy related illness and complication may be 1 in 50 or as high as 1 in 14 (Mahler H, 1987); the current or recent census estimates for maternal death stands at 287000 (WHO,2012).85% of these maternal death are in sub Saharan Africa and south Asia, Yet many of these illness and complications women face are preventable or avoidable given adequate maternal access to emergency obstetric care (EmOC).

Grepin and Klugman asserts that the negligence of women health, more so maternal health is casually related to discrimination in access to Education, employment and economic opportunities (Grepin KA and Klugman J, 2013). Given the importance of women health to development progress, it is surprising that female leadership in the health sector is sparse. In the current census estimates, Uganda's maternal death stands at 4,700; the adult lifetime risk of maternal death of current fifteen year old girls is 1 in 49 (WHO, 2012). These maternal death and lifetime risk for young girls is high for Uganda though positive strands have been made, we can't overlook these rates.

Women's roles in decision making as leaders is key. There is growing evidence that when women participate in policy and decision making, it improves their own lives, and the education of their children and the welfare of the whole family improves. Participation of women in decision making improves the distribution of resources, and sustainability of development programs. Women leaders can influence policies on maternal health and women's empowerment so other women benefit, policies that improve the welfare of the Nation are more likely to be implemented if women leaders are in decision making positions in the health sector (World Bank, 2011).

Therefore the question of how women leadership in the health sector has resulted into better performance in health service delivery is critical; the study seeks to explore the relationship between women leadership in the health sector and maternal health services, a critical focus on women leaders' performance in the health sector and delivery of maternal health services.

1.1 Background on women leadership and health services

Globally, nearly million young women die each year because of maternal complications and other health risk factors such as breast cancer and cervical cancer; these diseases are preventable in resource rich countries. Sub-Saharan Africa women have a life time maternal mortality risk of 1 in 31, which is hundred times higher than women in wealthier countries. (Lozano et al, 2012) Maternal health affects families badly; children whose mothers have died are three times more likely to die than other children whose mothers still alive. (Ronsmans et al, 2010) The neglect of women's health is casually related to discrimination in access to education, employment, and economic opportunities. (Grepin & Klugman, 2013) Because of high rates of preventable mortality among women in resource-poor countries, women's health is a central focus of global health. Of the eight millennium development goals established by United Nations to eradicate extreme poverty, two focused or specifically targeted women health (United Nations, 2015).

The significance of women in the health sector is seen and acknowledged world over, despite the importance of women in health care service delivery, female leadership in the health sector is very sparse; women constitute of 26% of health ministers in Africa and 24% of directors in the global health centers at the 50 U.S medical schools; the principle stated by Anne-marie Slaughter in the Atlantic. "Only when women wield power in sufficient numbers will we create society that genuinely works for all women." (Slaughter, 2012) This principle is very key if the impact of women in the health sector is to felt and create a society that works for all.

Gender gap exist in leadership in many fields, including government, business, law and educations and global health which has a troubling gap because women's health and reducing unjust health inequalities are central to subject matter, closing this gap will not in itself solve all women's health problem but will be the first step(Jennifer A et al 2014)

The main benefits of women leadership has been demonstrated in the development work all over the world; a recent study carried in India revealed that, for every one-standard deviation increase in female held seats in the district council, neonatal mortality dropped by 1.5% (Bhalotra S, Clot-Figuras 1, 2014) women leaders were also more likely to support health facilities, antenatal care, and immunizations. (Bhalotra S, 2014). In a related study also created in India the investigators revealed that women were more likely to invest in public works such as drinking clean water while men mostly invested in things that concerns men like irrigation systems for farming.

(Chattopadhyay R, Duflo E, 2004) after a decade of implementation of these random leadership assignments, adolescent girls in the villages with female leaders received significantly more education, and higher job aspirations and spent less time on domestic chores than girls in the villages without female leaders (Beaman L et al 2012)

In rural Afghanistan a study was carried among women who were randomly assigned to a program that requires 50% female council representation, compared with women in villages without the requirements, the women in villages with 50% female council representation, were significantly more likely to generate income and to rate their leaders as acting in the best interest of the entire village (Beath et al 2012).

In most societies, women are inferior species, because women are denied access to honoured and utilitarian roles allowed for men in these societies/communities, religion and governance and health governance, exclusively belong to men, conjugal right to choice is denied to women; all these discriminatory practices hinder women's possibility for impacting development in the communities. (Endale A.H. (2014)

Studies carried on how to put an end to the daunting siege to maternal health, focus on community based interventions to improve maternal health outcomes (Audrey Prost et al 2013; Sonia Lewycka et al 2013), the main focus is on grass root women's role in maternal health, the collective efforts or action of women in groups, nevertheless community based interventions are important in the fight against maternal mortality, neonatal death and other maternal health related cases; but to be able to tackle this challenge there is a need to explore intervention possibilities from all angles, not only focusing on the bottom intervention strategies but also top strategies or interventions should be sought in the health sector to address maternal mortality, neonatal and infant death in the community; a wide range of interventions should be explored from community to health institutional leadership and more so seek women leaders' role in promoting maternal health services in the community and also establish the performance of these women in terms of maternal health delivery services.

According to Domingo et al (2015) women's use of their interests while simultaneously recognizing the diversity of their experiences and their uniqueness. For example, women have different experiences of motherhood but, in politically constrained environments such as in pre-

transition Latin America, women have been able to use their gendered roles as ‘mothers’, and the legitimacy this gives them, to challenge rights abuses in a way that would not have been possible for men (Domingo et al.,2015).

The lack of decision making power limits women’s access to health care and negatively affect maternal health outcomes. In many societies, many control household expenditures and decision making in the family and families may be reluctant to use scarce resources for women’s health or nutritional needs. Although men may be the principal decision-makers on seeking health services, there may be little communication with their wives about their health during pregnancy and the postpartum period. (WHO, 2005) In many countries, significant percentages of women reported their husband alone make decision regarding their health, for example, Burkina Faso (74.9 per cent), Zambia(46.5 per cent) Armenia (20.2 per cent),Nepal (51 per cent) and Haiti (21.3 per cent).(UNICEF,2006)

The chance of dying is much greater in poor countries. Developing countries account for 99% of the global maternal deaths, majority of which are in sub Saharan Africa and south Asia (WHO, 2012). Disparities are enormous; the lifetime risk of maternal mortality in women living in sub Saharan Africa is over 47 times greater than for those in the United States. (WHO, 2012)

In a study carried at Malawi in the district of Mchinji by Sonia Lewycka et al(2013) on the effect of women’s groups volunteer peer counselling on rate of mortality using 2x2 factorial, cluster randomized trial among 185,888 people, their findings reveals that community mobilization through women’s groups and volunteers peer counsellor health education are methods to improve maternal and child health outcomes in the poor rural areas in Africa; this study reveals the importance of women groups and volunteer peer counselling in the reduction of maternal and infant mortality rates, if mobilization done in the community is effective it would result to a reduction in mortality (Sonia Lewycka et al, 2013).

Uganda is still one of the most affected nations in terms of poor quality of health services and outcomes (Darison O.K and Paul Okiira, 2014) in the world, despite the positive rates of economic growth in the recent years; the quality of many public health facilities is still poor. They are characterized by under paid and demoralized staff, shortages in trained personnel and medical equipment (Deininger and Mpuga, 2005). The health sector reforms in Uganda focused on

expanding and improving the health network; the decentralization of responsibilities for the provision of health services from the ministry of health to the district, was to bring major services in the health sector at local levels and improve on the administration and efficiency in the delivery of health services (Hutchinson, 1999)

In study of decentralization and public health sector in Uganda, Akin et al (2001) shows evidence that decentralization tends to promote health spending on less public type of goods such as Civil works, equipment purchase and vehicles at the expense of true public goods mainly primary health care including family planning, malaria control, maternal and child health, they concluded that decentralization under provide certain important health services relative to a centralized system. (Akin et al 2001).

The public health service delivery in Uganda is organized into three major levels; national referral, regional referral and District/rural hospitals; the facilities are further graded as health centre II (parish), health centre III (Sub-county) or health centre IV (HSD); they work on referral basis, Health centre provides basic preventive and curative services, managed by an enrolled Nurse, midwives and Nursing assistants. Health centre III is managed by a Clinical Officer, an enrolled Nurse, midwives and nursing assistants; it includes inpatient health services, maternity ward and Laboratory services; the sub district health centre IV are well equipped with a medical officer, clinical officer, Nurses, midwives, nursing assistants, laboratory technician and the assistants; health inspector, Dentist, accounts assistant and support staffs. It also provides surgical services in addition to other general services, it constitutes the first referral and usually has emergency care (Darlison O.K and Paul Okiira, 2004; MoH).

Adjumani district is located in the regions of west Nile, the district has a total of 16 health centre III, these health centres are saturated within ten sub-counties yet maternal health services in the district are under performing, maternal mortality and infant mortality are still high in the district, many government programs and NGO programs have been implemented in the different health centre to address these shortfalls, but the situation is still alarming. (Adjumani district health office, 2005)

Therefore, it is against this background that the study seeks to explore and determine the effect of women leadership on maternal health service delivery in Adjumani, the key concern is how women

leadership in the health sector helps in reducing maternal deaths, infant mortality, neonatal deaths and morbidity in the community; as seen in the background discussion that many interventions to address issues of maternal mortality are community based interventions which involves the women in the communities, but no efforts or less has been directed to study the performance of women leaders in health sector on health services delivery.

1.2 Problem Statement

Maternal health reflects the level of social justice and degree of respect of women's rights in society. Women's rights to receive good-quality health services is guaranteed when their basic human rights to education, nutrition, safe environment, to economic resources and to participation in decision making are met (WHO, 1999).

Irrespective of the above conception, every year, more than 289,000 women die during pregnancy or child birth. Most of these deaths are preventable (WHO, 2013). Atleast 12 million women have severe maternal complications (Stanton, brandes, (2012).

The chance of dying is much greater in poor countries. Developing countries account for 99% of the global maternal deaths, majority of which are in sub Saharan Africa and south Asia (WHO, 2012). Disparities are enormous; the lifetime risk of maternal mortality in women living in sub Saharan Africa is over 47 times greater than for those in the United States. (WHO, 2012)

Among the 122 million women who have a live birth yearly, 10 percent suffer complications and disability, (Huda FA, et al, 2012); Singhs, Darroch J, 2012); Maternal mortality is part of a range of maternal ill-health that affects children's, mothers health, development and ability to productively contribute to their communities and societies.

Reducing maternal mortality requires coordinated, long-term efforts at the household and community level as well as at the level of national legislation and policy formation, especially in the health sector. Long-term political commitment is essential for reviewing national laws and policies in the area of family planning and adolescent health ensuring availability of skilled attendants at birth, regulation of health practices, and the organisation of health services (WHO, 1999).

Uganda is a signatory to many international and regional covenants (CEDAW, Beijing platform for action, the millennium development goals (MDGs), and sustainable development goals). Moreover, the constitution of Uganda 1995 and the local government Act 1997; guarantee women basic human dignity and rights, political freedom and equality at the local levels especially in matters that affect them and their families such as health care, education, water and sanitation (Nabacwa M, 2001).

Women representation in leadership at the health sector is very crucial to the effective delivery of maternal health care, the more women are represented in leadership the more focus is placed on the needs of women, more so maternal health; with more representation of women in leadership positions in the health sector effective decisions can be taken to better the health of mothers and their children; having control over resources can allow for better allocation where resources can be prioritised for maternal needs; which results to better maternal health care (Domingo et al 2015).

Although women's basic human and health rights are known and well recorded maternal health services in most parts of Uganda has diminished. For instance, there is non-attendance of antenatal care in the rural areas, poor health facilities, and inadequacy of medical practitioners and men's negative attitudes towards maternal health services. In rural areas men do not encourage their wives to attend antenatal care; most believe men are key decision makers while women are caretakers. Due to this misconception in communities women are excluded in many decision making activities both at household and community levels. (GHI, 2011)

Maternal health care in Adjumani district, has lagged behind, with the little resources allocated to the health sector, the maternal sector sometimes go unheard of; women have to travel long distances to attend antenatal services; even delivery sometimes is carried at home because of the distances of the health units from the women in the district: women leadership at the health sector in the district is at 41.25 %; the health centre workers composed of 90% of women. (Adjumani District Report, 2015)

Despite having women in health leadership positions in Adjumani district, there is little improvement on maternal health services; in cases where women become leaders in the health sector, little is said over their performance in the health sector; and their leadership impact on maternal health because of its centrality to women health.

Leadership and effective delivery of maternal health services go hand in hand. Even in general health service delivery, leadership is very key. Without effective leadership in any social organ, that organ is deemed to fail. For health institution such as the health centre III at the sub county level to deliver effectively, the leadership must be sound and clear for better performance. This research based on the data collected qualitatively analyses and present the issues raised by the respondents at the health centres.

The study examined the role played by women in leadership and policy making position and effects on maternal health services in Adjumani district by carrying a comparative analysis of the performance of maternal health services at health centre IIIs under women and men leadership in Adjumani district.

1.3 Study objectives

1.3.1 General objectives

The main objectives of the study was to assess effects of women leadership on maternal health services; especial to assess whether women involvement in health leadership make maternal health services any better than it's under male leadership in Adjumani district.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

1. To determine the roles women in leadership play in promoting maternal health services in Adjumani district.
2. To examine the attitudes and perceptions of maternal health service users (clients) on women leadership in the health sector of adjumani district.
3. To identify barriers and constrains that affects women in health leadership in adjumani district and measures to overcome them.
4. To assess how women leadership and presence in decision making roles has influenced maternal services in adjumani district.

1.3.3 Research Questions

What roles do women leaders play in maternal health service delivery?

What are the attitudes and perceptions of service users (clients) on women leaders in the health sector?

What are the barriers and constraints that affect women in health leadership and measures to overcome them?

How has women leadership and presence in decision making roles influenced maternal health services?

1.4 Significance of the study

Ugandan women in health leadership face significant challenges in running their daily office work because of the stereotypes and discriminatory rules and practices in places of work; and also have to take care of their responsibilities as mothers at home; on top of that women's work are disturbed by the existence and/or non-existence of policies that aim to improve the lot of women; the research study therefore aims to shed light on how women in health leadership are affected by the health environment; and how their position as leaders in the health sector has resulted to better maternal health services delivery and what best strategies can help women in leadership provide selfless services to achieve better maternal services in the country.

1.5 Definition of the key terms

This section lays down the main concepts used in research and defines them in the context of the study that is intended to be carried in Adjumani district

1.5.1 Leadership

The concept of leadership in social science is underdeveloped or its definition is not clearly defined; it means different things to different people in different communities; it focuses on individual traits, qualities and capabilities. For instance, vision, charisma and ability to achieve majority concrete goals (Batliwala, 2010; Lynne de Ver, 2008). The term leadership in this study is defined as the exercise of influence: a form of persuasion in the pursuit of individual or organizational goals. Leadership thus involves the capabilities for, and process of, mobilizing people and resources to secure a desired outcome.

Therefore effectiveness in leadership is achieved when it translates into outcomes, whatever the precise content of those might be. It is this capacity of influence that is important in connecting voice to the effectuation of change. Leadership, therefore, whether collectively or individually represented, enables the 'power over' others to achieve change or drive certain outcomes (Rowlands, 1997; Higgitt, 2011).

The issues that emerged in relation to leadership based on the in depth interview with health centre III in charges and health workers more especially the midwives who are basically trained to tackle the issues of mothers health during the pregnancy, until the child is born normal and safely and the mothers health is also safe. During the interview with district officials and health workers, focus group discussions with mothers. Leadership was looked at as an important factor in the success of any type of service delivery not only in health services and especially maternal health. Respondents had different views on what leadership was but majority focused on leadership as an act of providing guidance to achieve a common goal in the health sector.

1.5.2 Women participation

According to Beall (1996) participation refers to ‘processes by which organized groups in the community (and individuals within them) identify and articulate their interests, negotiate change with others, and transform organizational life and their role within it’. It is essential to include a gender perspective in participatory processes to be able to respond to the diversity of people and practices, and break hierarchies. Participatory planning processes need to be gender-transformative (Kabeer 2005). Responding to women’s needs according to their realities, but without limiting women to the care role, and without reproducing gender stereotypes; transformative in the sense of promoting women’s ability to challenge these roles and stereotypes. (Sara Ortiz and Blanca Gutierrez, 2015)

1.5.3 Maternal Health

The world health organization (2011) the term Maternal health comprises the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. Health problems during pregnancy may have serious consequences, not only for the woman but also for her child, her family, and her community. Although motherhood is often a positive and fulfilling experience, for too many women birth is associated with suffering, ill-health, and even death (WHO 2011). Access to appropriate maternal healthcare services is a fundamental right. Seventy-five percent of maternal deaths occur during childbirth and the postpartum period, and the vast majority of these deaths are avoidable. Provisional of skilled care for all women before, during and after childbirth is a key strategy for saving women’s lives and ensuring the best chance of delivering a healthy infant (WHO 2004; save the children 2010). ANC and delivery care are considered basic component in any maternal healthcare program (Zanconato G, et al, 2006).

1.6 Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework above presents the main concepts that underlines the study; it explains how the key elements considered in women leadership (representation, decision making, resource control and allocation) influences maternal health service delivery, which includes antenatal care, family planning, postnatal and neonatal services, child immunization which are influenced by socio-cultural factors, the level of women education, women experience in leadership, women access to information and their level of connection or networks, these factors dictates on the level of maternal health services the community receive under women leadership and hence may directly or indirectly results to better indicators for maternal health or worsen maternal health indicators in the District.

Women representation in leadership at the health sector is very crucial to the effective delivery of maternal health care, the more women are represented in leadership the more focus is placed on the needs of women, more so maternal health; with more representation of women in leadership positions in the health sector effective decisions can be taken to better the health of mothers and their children; having control over resources can allow for better allocation where resources can be prioritised for maternal needs; which results to better maternal health care (Domingo et al, 2015)

1.7 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework I used to guide this research is transformational leadership theory. This theory explains well women leadership in the health setting.

1.7.1 Transformational leadership theory

According to Simola et al. (2012), transformational leadership as a type of leadership in which interactions among interested parties are organized “around a collective purpose” in such a way that “transform, motivate, and enhance the actions and ethical aspirations of followers.” Transformational leadership is a leadership style that seeks positive transformations “in those who follow” and that achieves desired changes through the “strategy and structure” of the organization (Geib and Swenson, 2013).

Transformational leadership is characterized by several patterns of behaviour. First, it employs the charisma of leaders in order to gain respect, trust and in still pride in stakeholders. Charisma entails provision of a common vision and sense of mission necessary for transformation and required outcomes. Secondly, inspiration were leaders use symbols to redirect followers’ efforts; they express in a simplistic manner and communicate clearly the higher expectations. Thirdly, intellectual stimulation were Leaders stimulate employees by emphasizing rationality and creativity in problem-solving situations. Finally, transformational leadership offers individualized consideration: leaders treat employees individually offering them personal attention and, whenever necessary, they provide coaching and advise to those employees (Bass, 1990)

Whereas there are many theories that explain women leadership in the health sector and health outcomes more especially maternal health services, this study used this particular theory because it is specific to leadership, which in turn is important in achieving maternal health service outcomes in the health setting of Uganda. Better out comes of maternal health services of ANC, Immunization, family planning, post-natal services can be achieved as a result of leadership that is transformatory in nature. The study deem transformation theory to explain women leadership in the health sector.

1.8 Scope of the study

1.8.1 The geographical scope

The study was carried in Adjumani District. Adjumani district, is located in northern part of Uganda shares boundaries with Amuru district, Moyo district and Arua, it was granted district status in 1997 May from Moyo district by the government. It composed of east Moyo County which together with west Moyo County previously made up Moyo district. At independence 1962, it was known as Madi district. Adjumani and Moyo districts are separated by Albert Nile. Adjumani district is boarded by the Republic of Sudan to the North, Gulu to the East and South by Arua, Moyo and Yumbe district in the west. The district has over 232813 people; 111503 are males and 121310 are females as per the 2014 national population and housing census (district development plan 2005-2008, Adjumani).

Adjumani district was granted district status in 1997 and as stated earlier on that maternal health service delivery has diminished in the district, there is need to find out why maternal health in the district is still underperforming though the district was granted self-administration long time ago. In addition to this, in 2014 there was an influx of refugees from the neighbouring country of south Sudan. This has resulted to the increase in the population of service users in the district, it's therefore crucial to find out how the health leadership has addressed this issues in order to ensure that maternal health services meet the need of the increasing population in the district.

THE MAP OF ADJUMANI DISTRICT SHOWING THE HEALTH CENTRES II, III, AND V

1.8.2 Content scope

The research examined women leadership and maternal health care; the main focus was placed specifically on how women leadership at health centre III levels impacts maternal health service delivery in Adjumani district; women involvement in leadership, and also assessment of their performance in relation to the men in the health sector in Adjumani district.

Maternal health care in Adjumani district, has lagged behind, with the little resources allocated to the health sector, the maternal sector sometimes go unheard of; women have to travel long distances to attend antenatal services; even delivery sometimes takes place at home because of the distances of the health units from the women in the district: women leadership at the health sector in the district is at 41.25 %; the health centre workers composed of 90% of women (Adjumani, 2015).

1.8.3 Time Scope

The research captured data related to women leadership and maternal health services for a period of 10 years, from 2008 to the present, information written related to the subject being investigated was captured in the study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews related literature on women in leadership and maternal health services globally, regional and national and also tries to conceptualize the terms used in the research study by have a detailed analysis of the concepts from previous researches done in related fields by different authors from different fields and disciplines.

2.2 Women roles in leadership and maternal health services

This section of the literature reviews focus on the role women play in leadership and how this role has impact on maternal health services; focus is also placed on the historical context of women leadership in the health sector, how the issue of women in leadership has been evolving from the past generation to the current; this section also focuses on the role women play in global health and how women have ascended to this role in the global context, it's vital to examine the historical context of women in health leadership and their position in global health in order to understand women leadership position in the health sector.

2.2.1 Historical context of women in health leadership

Women in the health care is a concept that existed long ago in the field of health, during ancient times women were given responsibility such as taking care of the sick and the injured, this act resulted to a gendered workforce in the health sector, however even during this time the kind of work in which they were entangled was more of caretaking, then leading in the health sector; from the historical path of the women in health care, the issue of leadership evolved later, though earlier on women were involved in caretaking, then leading in the health sector; from the historical path of the women in health care, the issue of leadership evolved later, though earlier manifested bravery and potential to do what man can do in the health sector and do better, though men were still conservative to relinquish the field of leadership to the women in the sector but it became more evident in the future that women are better leaders compared to the men if just given the platform in which they can exercise that right. (Hasen-feld, 1992)

The struggle for equality between men and women is a long due battle that has been fought for centuries in history which at its peak in the past; the rights to vote (suffrage) and affirmative actions

in most countries were attempts to increase equality among genders as societies moved from egalitarian to become industrialized, there was need for more workers and by then men were the majority workers, during the period of wars; most men went for war and left their previous positions of work, couple with the need ammunition there was need to fill the gap left by men; and women decided to take responsibilities by themselves and do the work that was prior done by men of war production, the decision made by women to take responsibility of work to support the ongoing war was a very huge step for women and realization of their potential to work and do what men use to do, made a huge impact on their entry into the work force. (Christian et al, 2010).

According to Christian et al (2010) women continued to work even after the war had halted and became more visible in the workforce and played their roles in work places very competently and well with no distraction and jeopardy, in fact they did perform better than men but given the existing structural injustices in the society they were not allowed to rise above men, but the women given them opportunities to realize their potentials and opened doors of an imaginable opportunity. (Christian et al; 2010)

In a study carried by Mano-Negrin, 2004 (Mano-Negrin, 2004), revealed a significant increase in participation of women in the work force or the labor market without a parallel decrease of gender wage gaps. Bosak (Bosak&Sczerny, 2008) also revealed in their study that women perceive themselves less suitable for high positions because the perceived notion that they do not associate with masculine characteristics of men.

In the current world, majority of the healthcare workforce is made up of women; according to the UN bureau of labor statistics (Statistic, 2013), 75.8% of those employed in hospitals in 2011 were women. More so, women occupied nearly 71.3 of the first and mid-level officer and management positions in the private hospital industry in 2012 (EEOC, 2012).

Many international conventions, regulations and national policies emphasis the issues of equality for both man and woman in the workforces and equal treatment both the law but regardless of these efforts from all these international, regional and nation actors; there is still biases in the work place that still contributes to the discrimination against women in the workforce, more so in environments that is predominantly male; these biases affects the prevalence of women in leadership, job performance, and male dominated careers. (Christian et al, 2010)

The persistent notion of gender bias in the community to the extent that women themselves cannot escape acknowledging it and even falling susceptible to its ideas, this is commonly a recurring problems in several patterns, were women fill vulnerable and out of place because they have no female role model in the position of leadership or power to relate to; this lack or absence of stimuli results in the chances of women to take on leadership role (Carbonell & Castro, 2008).

2.2.2 Women leadership in global health

The literature analysed supports the principles that leaders' gender influence both their decisions and the welfare of women in the areas of jurisdiction; achieving gender parity in global health leadership will affect global policy and practice. (Jennifer et al 2014)

Jennifer and others (2014) pointed out that some generational differences exists; more young women in 2013 were more interested in global health than in the past years, and percentages of female leaders may increase as this generation grows old, however parity in leadership has not been achieved despite women's interest in health issues and the centrality of women's health.

Many strategies have been implemented in different fields including politics and business, which has resulted into the promotion of many women into the senior management positions. (Barsh J, Yee L, 2014) after the 1994 fourth conference on women in Beijing, 189 governments signed the Beijing platform for action, agreeing to a target of 30% of their National decision making positions should be held by women. (United Nations 1995)

As a result of the signing of the Beijing platform for action by the 189 governments, there have been a doubling in the position of women in decision making positions more especially in National assemblies, and the highest rate have been registered by national governments that have added the female quota requirement to boost women involvement in the leadership role of the country. (UNIFEM, 2009) this is a clear evidence that policies and regulations enacted by international, regional organization and national regulation can have a profound impact on increasing women leadership in many respective national governments. (Inter-parliamentary Union, 2012)

In a nut shell, the role of women leadership is significant for progressive development of the health sector, as elaborated in the historical context, women assumed roles and responsibilities in the health sector and other sectors when their men counterparts went to fight wars and thus they were able to demonstrate that women are capable despite the wrong notion about them previously and

slowly women assumed roles in different sector of the economy, which has overtime resulted to the increased participation of women in global health, their participation has enabled women to fight for the rights to safe motherhood and safe delivery in the health sector.

2.3 Attitudes and perceptions on women leadership

This section deals with the attitudes and perceptions of communities on women leadership in the health sector; under this sub-section, focus is placed on the impact of the social institutions on women leadership in the health sector; the issue of attitudes and perceptions is important because it reveals the positions of the communities and social institutions within a given setting on women leadership in the health sector and this determines the efficiency of these women in leadership; focus is placed on social institutions and women leadership, perceptions and views on women leadership

2.3.1 Social institutions and women leadership

According to Jutting and others (2008) Social institutions are defined a formal and informal laws, social norms and practices that shape or restrict the decisions, Choices or behaviours of groups, communities and individuals; social institutions also set parameters of what decisions, choices or behaviours are deemed acceptable or unacceptable in a society, social institutions play a very a very important role in defining gender roles and relations; however these social institutions are not fixed do vary across countries, region and communities and keep changing overtime; we can't say that social institutions are bad or good, but the nature of the social institutions defines that type of social institution in existence; discriminatory social institution restrict and exclude women and girls and consequently limit their access to opportunities, resources and power which negatively upon developmental outcomes: through their influence on the unequal distribution of power between men and women in the private sphere of the family, economic and the public sphere, these social institutions constrain the opportunities of men and women but more specially women in a male dominated society and their capabilities to live life they value(Sen, 1999). According Sen (2007) social institutions more especially the discriminatory social institutions reflect underlying gendered power relations in communities across the globe which make them more difficult but not impossible to transform.

Prevalent social institutions in many communities exert their influence both directly and indirectly (Jutting and Morrison 2005). These laws, social norms and practices can directly influence

women's social and economic role, for instance not allowing women to access bank loans, preventing women from owning Land or restricting women's ability to move freely in public space; a very good institution that ascribes values to son over daughters, this attribution affect the economic values of women and even impact on their ability to lead because of the existing norms that values men over women.

Discriminatory social institutions play an important role in determining opportunities and outcomes for women and girls and subsequently, development outcomes are impacted; early marriages for girls more especially with a wide age gaps between spouses is linked with lower educational attainment for girls (Ambrus and field, 2008; Lloyd and mensch, 2008), this could result to high rate of adolescent fertility, higher rate of infant mortality, increased poor maternal health and vulnerability to HIV(Bruce and Clark, 2004; UNFPA, 2004) The exclusion of women and girls from public, social, political and economic spaces due to discriminatory practices also limits their access to education, employment and health services (Jones et al, 2010)

2.3.2 Perceptions and views on women leadership

Highlights under this section is placed on the perception and views on women leadership in the community and more so in the health sector; focusing on women leaders and authority; people's perceptions and views on women leadership.

2.3.2.1 Women leaders and authority

Leadership and authority are features that have been commonly associated with the male sex and the positions of power and authority in leadership are linked to such generalizations; they are instances where women are segregated into profession that ultimately reduce the possibility of exercising autonomy and supervisory authority (Jaffee, 1989). We often witness that when it comes to consideration for position, women are subject bias subdues their attempts at equality and fair judgements and most employers prefer male to the female counterparts (Goktepe & Craig, 1989).

The persistent of such notions of gender bias make women susceptible to its ideas and even women in some instances acknowledge its reality; this problem has made women feeling vulnerable and out of place because they have no one to look as female role model in leadership positions,

resulting into a reduction in chances of women take on the leadership roles in the public spheres (Carbonell & Castro, 2008).

The finding of Carbonell and Castro revealed when women are confronted with female role model they are most likely to take the leadership role but when faced with a male role model the results were underwhelming however the men in the study felt indifference when faced with either model, which reveals the common acceptance for male superiority or dominance (Carbonell & Castro, 2008)

2.3.2.2 Perceptions and views on women leadership

perceptions of the meaning of equality are different among individuals according to their self-interest; a study carried by Koch and others (2005) that sought to look into the changes in perceptions of women in leadership, with an increase in women leadership the study compares the change in beliefs now and the beliefs held 20 years ago; in the result there was a tendency for gender association that went with social perceptions; men were often associated with terms such as hard, strong, and aggressive whereas women were judged as soft, sentimental and delicate.

Although data revealed a shift towards associating women with leadership however the correlation was not significant, despite efforts the gaps still exist in positions in leadership, we can't dismiss the fact that shift in leadership is being evidenced though with a small percentage.

A study done by Haslam and Ryan (2008) that focused on the suitability of the women and men in leadership of failing or succeeding organizations; it examined the inequalities that women encounter when trying to advance in their workforce, and the study hypothesized that women are appointed to leadership positions in organizations when risk of failure and criticism are high; the results revealed in general women are preferred over men; the results revealed that men were selected over women when the organization is succeeding or performing better and women become suitable individuals to take leadership when an organization or Company is declining, the study revealed that there exist preferences of men to successful companies, this may be as a result of perceptions and beliefs of the individual who appoint leaders to positions.

Wolf, and Fligsteing (2009) did a study that looked at factors that contribute to the unequal distribution of women compared to men in positions of authority focusing on education, experience, tenure, marriage, children that help map how and why some individuals are in

positions of power. It looked at the composition of the workplace and situational beliefs of employers and women in leadership; the study concluded that men are given more power and authority than women.

In a nut shell, there are different perceptions, views and attitudes about women taking leadership position in the health sector and other different disciplines, due to regulations and international conventions women are able to take up leadership in different fields however they level of exercising authority is not comparable to that of men, because men have excess power and authority given to them by the community compared to women, they are decisions that are community deem right for men to make but not women by this much authority is given to men but less for women, perceptions and attitudes are subject to change over time and it is an important contributory factor for the success of any leadership and that's why it important to talk about it in this review.

2.4 Challenges and obstacles faced by women in leadership

This sub section deals with the challenges and obstacles faced by women in leadership; there are many factors that women leaders face in leadership in the health sector, but also general women ascending to leadership position also face challenges, so this section focus on the challenges faced by women leaders focusing on women leaders and the grass root women; and challenges experienced by women in leadership; culture, traditions and women leadership.

2.4.1 Women leaders and the grass root women

The biggest problems women leaders face is the gap between women elites and women at the grassroots level in Africa. For instance in South Africa, since the acceptance of the neoliberal macroeconomic framework, growth, employment, and redistribution, the gap between the rich and the poor has increased dramatically; The neoliberal commitment to market solutions leads to women's disproportionate vulnerability to poverty, given women's labor market disadvantages and responsibilities for care. In the South African case, many women are further disadvantaged by being poorly educated or illiterate; there is no social safety net for poor women who do not have children, do not look after disabled relatives, or are not old enough to be entitled to an old-age pension. The lack of a comprehensive social protection system aggravates the life of poorest of the poor, often leading to conditions of destitution. What is needed from women leaders is "double militancy" (Becwith, 2000), whereby women are not only active in the state but also take an active

interest in constituencies of women or groups that represent women so that grassroots level women may feel that their interests are represented in government. (Amanda Gouws, 2008)

2.4.2 Challenges experienced by women in leadership

Women in leadership in pursuit of their work responsibilities and a bid to balance their domestic role find themselves in a dilemma; coupled with the structural challenges that are inherent in our communities with bars women from doing responsibilities and duties in places of work.

The relationships many women have with their mentors, bosses and female co-workers. Most employees tend to bond through similar interests. Since there tend to be few executive women; many women are unable to find a female mentor. Laff (2006) finds that women are inhibited in the workplace because of their limited access to capable mentors. Many people prefer to have mentors of the same gender because they tend to understand the challenges most commonly faced. Men do not face the same barriers, have the same family issues, and many times simply do not want to mentor a woman. The needs of women from their mentors also tend to differ from the needs of men. Many women claim to need more encouragement, an example to follow, and simply more tasks to complete. Male mentors tend to be resistant to mentor a woman because they perceive women as more emotional, not as skilled at problem-solving, and because of the risk of workplace sexual harassment issues (Hanson, 2008).

The era of globalization presents many new challenges for women. Senior level managers and top executives now have even more responsibility and higher expectations than before. Due to the time pressures and relocations of many businesses, top executives have had to move to new towns, cities, and countries. This presents a large barrier for many women with families and a working spouse or significant other (Wellington, Krogg, & Gerkovich, 2003). Perhaps more surprisingly, the largest problem, however, has not been unable to accept the culture shock and fail in their new environments. Similarly, women may also experience resistance in other cultures to female leadership. Many countries will simply not deal with a women executive because of their beliefs and perceptions that women are incapable of doing business effectively (Strout, 2001).

Many women, in addition to the roles they hold in their companies, they remain the primary caretakers for their families (Hughes, Ginnett, & Curphy, 2009). As the time constraints and demands of a job become more important upon, promotion forces many women to choose between

family and Career. According to Jack and Suzy Welch (2007), very few women CEOs and women executives have children due to the affect it would have on their career. Conversely, many women have voluntarily left their jobs due to family decisions (Baxter, 2000; Wallace, 2008). While a decreasing number of women are taking pregnancy or childcare leaves, 32% of women still leave their jobs once they have children. Also, once a woman has children she is much more reluctant to travel and work long hours due to their responsibilities at home further hindering her promotion likelihood (Woodard 2007; Hewlett, 2002; Lyons & McArthur, 2005).

Past perceptions of leadership skills, competence, and assertiveness may hinder the ability of women to succeed in management. Many companies associate masculine characteristics with success and achievement. These include assertiveness, aggressiveness, and task-oriented leadership abilities (Jogulu&Wood 2006; Envick, 2008). Other stereotypes of women include the expectation of being modest, quiet, selfless, and nurturing (Eagly&Carl, 2003). These simple characteristics may be seen as non-executive material. Entities desire a leader who will execute, take criticism, and do what is best for the company at all cost (Nelson & Levesque 2007).

Leadership styles are closely associated with common perceptions and stereotypes of women leaders (Goff, 2005; Henderson, 2004). In early 1990 studies found that men emerged as task-oriented leaders more frequently than women who emerged as social leaders more frequently than men (Marrujo&Kliender, 1992). Due to the demands of leadership positions, it became a socially accepted (Ryan &Haslam, 2007). As time moved on, the social leadership style of women was more accepted and valued in some circumstances (Jogulu &Wood, 2006).

2.4.3 Cultures, traditions and women in leadership

In the African context, traditional beliefs and cultural attitudes regarding the role and status of women in society are still prevalent and many women are part of this system finding it difficult to dislocate from the cultural tradition lest they be detested (Kiamba, 2008). Despite women's education and entry into the job market, the woman's role is typically of homemaker. The man on the other hand is bread winner, head of the house and has a right to public life (Sadie, 2005). Sadie asserts that cultural attitudes are hostile to women involvement in decision making positions. Despite cultural attitude some women are able to transcend and rise to positions of leadership but more often than not, it means having to juggle cultural expectations with their leadership roles.

In society there is a belief that a good mother must give less effort and priority to work demands, she is therefore seen as less committed worker. Furthermore, Ridgeway (Ridgeway, 2001) added that this biased belief is likely to create barriers to women advancement in the workplace. These barriers make women lack opportunities to present their ideas, therefore reducing their influence over group decisions and in contrast according to Feugen and others(2004) they believe that societal judgement made towards mothers, employed fathers are regarded as better parents and more professionally competent (Feugen, Bienat, Haines, &Deaux, (2004). This notion includes the belief that mothers must do more than fathers to be labelled as good as good parents and that mothers are held to higher standards of responsibilities than fathers. Based on social role theory that guides judgement of mothers and fathers, full time employed mothers are judged as violating the norms of caretaker role, but employed fathers embody the provider role. As such, motherhood would have a detrimental effect on women's career opportunities but an enhancing effect on men's opportunities.

According to Nzomo (1995) amidst the several identified obstacles that prevent women from advancing to senior positions. He regards social cultural beliefs as the major barriers in this regard.

The beliefs emphasize the superiority of men and the inferiority of women, they form an integral part of the socialization process and gender education and training most men and women are exposed to from child hood based on the concept of role expectancy an individual develops through the years his or her own set of internalized values, beliefs, attitudes, ideals and aspirations.

Women in a nutshell faces a lot of challenges and obstacles in the communities and places of women were they take up leadership position and even in the health sector; right from the culture and traditions in most communities that prohibit women from assuming leadership roles in the communities; women leaders also have challenges in connecting with the grass root women; in most cases a gap is created between the leader and the local woman in the village but there is need to focus on this gap and address them to ensure efficient service delivery.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This section of the dissertation highlights the methodology employed in the study, the research employed qualitative descriptive research design; by carrying out a descriptive analysis of the nature of leadership and maternal health services provided at health centre IIIs in adjumani district. In-depth interviews, focus group and observation were employed for the purposes of gathering data and analysing the data collected from the field and also made inferences as pertaining the information got from the field.

3.2 Research design

Kumar (1999) stated that a research design is a procedural plan that is adopted by researchers to answer questions objectively, accurately, economically and with validity.

A traditional research design is a blueprint or detailed plan of how a research study is to be completed; operating variables for measurement, selecting a sample, collecting data and analysing the results of interest to the study, and testing the hypotheses (Thyer, 1993).

The researcher used a descriptive research design; this research design clearly brings out the performance of maternal health services in all the health centre III facilities in Adjumani district: by knowing maternal health service performance in the 16 health centre III, under the respective leadership. References are made as to whether maternal health services outcomes performs better under women leadership and suggestion also made to improve on women access to leadership position in the health sector.

The reason why I used a descriptive research design, this research design help provide answers to the questions of who, what, when, where, and how associated with a particular research problem; a descriptive study cannot conclusively ascertain answers to why. Descriptive research is used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena and to describe "what exists" with respect to variables or conditions in a situation.

3.3.1 Areas used for description in the study

3.3.1.1 Communication

Under this criteria the researcher's interest was to concentrate on Client-service provider relationship, that is, how leaders communicate to maternal health users; what's the interpersonal

relationship between leaders and maternal health service users and leader's relationship to the health workers; how do health in charges give feedback to maternal service users and follow up.

3.3.1.2 Maternal health facility status/quantity

The concern was on availability and quality of maternity ward and ward Capacity; Number of Beds in the ward; Availability of bed nets and usage; placenta hole availability; Sanitation i.e. bathrooms, toilets and dustbins. These are key indicators for better maternal health services.

3.3.1.3 Human resource management/ maternity workforce

In maternity workforce, the interest was on description/categories of workforce at the health centre; Qualifications/ training of health workers; on-going professional development; Workers motivation by health in charge; in-charge-workers relationship.

3.3.1.4 Maternal health services available at the health facility

The types of maternal health services at the health centres, i.e. Facility based delivery; Antenatal care (ANC); post-natal care; Family planning services offered; Immunization; was established and the quality of the services offered at the health centers.

3.3.1.5 Quality of maternity care provided

1. Effectiveness: how often women receive appropriate care throughout their pregnancy (ANC); Childbirth; postnatal period (first six weeks of delivery).
2. Safety: the incidences of outcomes of perinatal; Maternal mortality; Morbidity
3. Efficiency of maternal healthcare delivered and the systems that support it deliver value for money for both the government and Public

3.3.1.6 Maternal healthcare- consumer satisfaction

Maternal healthcare consumer satisfaction included personal expectations, the amount of support given by caregivers; the quality of the caregiver-patient relationship; Women's involvement in decision making

3.3.1.2 The Area of study

The area is occupied by Madi; their main activity is agriculture and fishing with few livestock rearing and trading activities Agriculture with main emphasis on food crops such as millet, potatoes, beans, and cassava. Cash crops include cotton and coffee. There is fishing on the River

Nile and trading activities at various trading centres. (Danish Assistance to the self-Reliance Strategy, September 2005).

3.4 Data Sources

To obtain the aim of this study, both primary sources and secondary sources was used for collection of data in order to do data analysis.

3.4.1 Primary data sources

This was gathered from the sample respondents who are the primary source of data for the study which was selected through sampling from the study population.

3.4.2 Secondary data sources

The main sources used for secondary data includes different books in the fields of gender and women studies, districts reports, internet sources (UN, UNDP, UNWOMEN websites) and other documented sources, alongside articles and journals.

3.5 Population and sample size

3.5.1 Study population

Is a collection of elements from which the sample for the study is actually selected? Accordingly, the study population for this research included medical practitioners in Adjumani district, DHT in Adjumani district, health workers at health unit centers and women who are the recipients of maternal health services.

3.5.2 Sample size

The key informants included 7 respondents, 2 people (LC5, CEO) who were selected purposively from the district. They were deemed to have the expected information that enabled the researcher get information on leadership and maternal health services issues with the district.

At the District Health Department, five (5) people were selected purposively from the district health department as key informants; these were the district health officer, who is in charge of the district health secretary and three members of the district health committee, these are focal person on health matters in the district, they provided expected information on women leadership and maternal health services in the district.

16 health centre IIIs in charges participated through an in-depth interview; the list of health unit in charges will be requested from the district health offices. The district has 16 health centre IIIs, therefore all the in charges were interviewed.

7 health workers at health centre III were interviewed on leadership and maternal health services in their respective facilities, a list of health workers at all health centre IIIs was requested from the district health officer and a simple random sampling employed to generate the list of participants to include in the study.

20 women participants were purposively selected to participate in a focus group discussion within the district, two focus group were conducted in two health facility (a male headed health facility and a woman headed health facility) where the participants were purposively selected, in order to get their views as maternal service consumers on maternal health service delivery, this was done to determine the satisfaction they got from the health centre and how they perceive the leadership of the health centre.

The total sample size for the study under investigation was 50 respondents, these included the health centre units in charge, district officials, respondents from the district health department and respondents from district headquarters.

3.5.3 Exclusion and inclusion Criteria

For inclusion in the focus group discussion, all mothers who have brought their children for immunization, ANC first visits and revisits were included as participants in the selected health facility at the time of discussion.

For the health unit in charges, the in charges should have completed atleast one year tenure as an in charge at the health centre for the person to participate in the study. Any person representing the in charge should have spent atleast two working years at the health centre. Health workers more especially the midwives should atleast have a certificate in midwifery to be included in the research as a participant.

The key informants to participate in this research study, they should have reached twenty five years and above, and served in their capacity in the office for atleast one year.

3.5.4 Sampling techniques

To select sample respondents from the total study population, both probability and non- probability sampling was employed, for the probability sampling the simple random sampling was used to determine health workers interviewed and a purposive sampling techniques for selecting twenty participants from the district; the use of purposively sampling allows for the selection of participants who had the needed information on leadership and maternal health services and willing to share it. (Ronjit Kumar (2005) page 179).

3.6 Method of data collection

This subsection outlines the methods employed for data collection during the research process. Three methods were used: which includes; in-depth interviews, focus group discussion and observation, explained in details below

3.6.1 In-depth interview

The researcher intends to use an in-depth interview with selected respondents to collect primary data from key informants; health unit in charge and health workers. An interview guide was developed in English because this category of respondents are civil servants deemed to use English and it is also easier to interview in English, which was used to collect raw data from the key informants from the district health department and district officials

3.6.2 Focus group discussion

Two sessions of focus group discussions was organized consisting of 10 women participants who were selected purposefully for the study; the women are recipients of maternal health services so they provided expected information on the level of satisfaction they got from the health centre III; in each sessions. This enabled the researcher get in-depth exploration of the issue at hand and be in position to examine the views of the people especially on women participation in leadership.

3.6.3 Observation

Observation combined with note taking was used to supplement on the data got from the in-depth interview and focus group discussion of women, to determine maternal health service performances under the leadership of women and men in the health sector. This helped to get useful information on the state of maternal health services in the different health centre IIIs in Adjumani district.

3.7 Data Analysis and interpretation

The study was a descriptive research study, so the researcher collected qualitative data. Data obtained from the field was recorded, edited, organized and then analyzed, interpreted and presented in relation to research questions. The data was analyzed manually and content analysis and thematic approach where data was grouped under the identified themes and sub-themes, and then identified the partner of ideas that develop, explain and theorized the outcomes.

3.8 Ethical issues

Consent by research respondents is the key to this research, before any information is got from the respondents, all research proceedings was explained to researcher participants and they consented before any information was obtained, he/she had to consent by signing a consent form, that indicated the respondent was not forced but offered voluntarily to participate in the research process.

Confidentiality of the information provided, was granted by the researcher and this was explained to the respondents before their participated in the research; the researcher explained to respondents that information given was treated with strict confidentiality, information was stored careful and after analysis destroyed and they were assured that the information they provided was not shared with a third party only for the purposes of achieving the aim of the research that was carried.

Participation in this study is voluntarily and non-monetary value is attached to it, there are times when the research respondents needed financial benefits for sharing information relevant to the research aim, the researcher had to explain to them the value of the research and the wrong with financial returns for their information.

CHAPTER 4

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter analyses, presents and discusses the findings that were collected by the researcher using the methodologies described in chapter three. Findings in this chapter are presented and discussed according to the study objectives to form major themes and sub- themes

4.1 characteristic of respondents

4.1.1 Age of research respondents

The age distribution of respondents was relatively fair; the respondents for this research were between the ages of 25 to 60+ years of age. 41.6% of the respondents were between 25-30 years of age and this age category had the majority of respondent for this research. Which clearly implies that majority of the health workers in the health sector are in the youth/young age group and in leadership, who are better positioned to cause better outcomes in the health. Another 16.6% of the respondents were between 31-35 years of age and 41-45 years of age, 8.3% between the ages of 36-40, 51-55 and 56+ years. None was in the age of 46-50 years of age. There are a few health workers or leaders in the elderly age group in the health, it implies that the health sector leadership and health workers and young and energetic and can cause positive transformation compared to the old age health workers.

Table 1: showing age categories of respondents

s/n	Category	respondents in each category
1	(25-30)	5
2	(31-35)	2
3	(36-40)	1
4	(41-45)	2
5	(46-50)	0

6	(51-55)	1
7	(56-above)	1

4.1.2 Positions held by respondents at health facilities

There is a clear indication that majority of the health workers in the health facilities are well trained and experienced to deliver, maternal health services to the clients-consumers in adjumani district, 8 of the health workers are clinical officers, this make 34.7 % of the health workers clinicians. 5 are nursing officers making 21.7 % of the health workers. 13 % are midwives. 4% senior clinical officer and 4% medical technician, 8% enrolled nurse and 13% enrolled midwife. In a nut shell the health workers at the 16 health centre IIIs in adjumani and all leaders of this health centers are experienced in their respective positons to deliver better outcomes for health and more so maternal health.

Table 2: positions of respondents at the health facility

S/N	Title/positions	Number in each category
1	Medical Clinical officer	8
2	Nursing officer	5
3	Midwife	3
4	Senior medical clinical officer	1
5	Medical health technician	1
6	Enrolled nurse	2
8	Enrolled midwife	3

4.1.3 Level of education of respondent

Better health service delivery are as a result of being educated, which also influences leadership. There is, therefore need to encourage professional development by pursuing further studies, as indicated 18(36%) of the respondents are diploma holders, 2(4%) holds advanced diploma, 4(8%) holds bachelor and 1(2%) holds masters. This is a clear indication, that both service consumers

and providers are atleast informed to a certain level of education, which results to better maternal health service delivery. A leader not educated would be an outfit in the health sector, I guess that would be a dream by in reality leaders need to be informed to lead health institutions to a common goal.

Table 3: level of education of respondents

s/n	Level of education	Number in each level
1	Primary	14
2	Secondary	6
3	Certificate	5
4	Diploma	18
5	Advanced Diploma	2
6	Bachelor (university)	4
7	Masters (university)	1

4.1.4 Qualification/specialization of respondents

Specialization is key to effective service delivery in any given health institution, in the health sector one cannot be “jack of all trade” probably one is deemed to fail in this case, most of the respondents I talked as key informants at the health centre and the DHT and district officials are specialist in their field.

6(23%) specialized in clinical and community health. 8 (31%) have qualified in clinical medicine.

3(11.5%) qualified in midwifery. 5(19%) specialized in nursing. 1(3.8%) qualified in laboratory technician, law, public administration and environmental health, this clearly implies that the health sector in adjumani comprise of qualified workers and leaders in their respective capacities, thus necessary for effective delivery of maternal health services in the district.

Table 4: specialization of respondents

s/n	Qualifications	Number of respondents
1	Clinical medicine and community health	6
2	Clinical medicine	8
3	Midwifery	3
4	Nursing/Nursing assistant	5
5	Laboratory technician	1
6	Lawyer	1
7	Public administration/MBA	1
8	Environmental health	1

4.1.5 Health workers team of service worked in the health sector

The number of years spent working in the health sector for the in charges and health workers interviewed makes 8 respondents in the category of 11 years to 15 years which makes the largest number of respondents having worked in the health within those ranges of years; 7 of the respondents both in charges and health workers are in the category of 1year to 5 years; 6 of the respondents are in the category of 6years to 10 years; 4 of the respondents are in the category of 16years to 30 above; 5 of the respondents are in the category of 1month to 1year; this team of service is for the health workers interviewed from the health facilities and the in charges of the health centre III in the district.

The team of service in the health sector is important because it dictates the level of experience of the health workers, the more experience a health worker is the better outcomes are delivered. Majority of the health workers have spent a considerable year in health service, this explains the better performance of other health centre. With experience comes improve health service delivery.

Table 5: term of service in the health sector

S/n	Team of services category	Respondents in each category
1	1month-1 year	5
2	1year-5years	7
3	6years-10years	6
4	11years to 15years	8
5	16years-30+ years	4

4.2 Key findings

This research managed to identify certain issues during the data collection processes relevant to the research, and analysed throughout the data collection phases. The identified issues was categorized into themes that enabled and eased the data analysis process, the identified themes where them sorted to fit in to the objective of the study for easy analysis and presentation

4.2.1 Leadership and maternal health service delivery

Leadership and effective delivery of maternal health services go hand in hand. Even in general health service delivery, leadership is very key. Without effective leadership in any social organ, that organ is deemed to fail. For health institution such as the health centre III at the sub county level to deliver effectively, the leadership must be sound and clear for better performance. This research based on the data collected qualitatively analyses and present the issues raised by the respondents at the health centres.

4.2.1.1 Leadership

The issues that emerged in relation to leadership based on the in depth interview with health centre III in charges and health workers more especially the midwives who are basically trained to tackle the issues of mothers health during the journey of pregnancy, until the child is born normal and safely and the mothers health is also safe. During the interview with district officials and health workers, focus group discussions with mothers. Leadership was looked at as an important factor in the success of any type of service delivery not only in health services and especially maternal health. Respondents had different views on what leadership was but majority focused on leadership as an act of providing guidance to achieve a common goal in the health sector.

“Leadership is process of organising, inspiring and influencing people to do an activity in order to achieve a common goal” (personal communication with a clinical officer at adjumani mission H/C III, October 2016)

The concept of leadership was well understood among the respondents, I interviewed. The health workers in the health centre III, attributed leadership to three main factors, namely; “organising, inspiring and influencing people” towards achieving a common organisational goal.

A few of the respondents I interviewed attributed leadership to the personality of the person who leads the health institution, because they believe leadership is all about the ability of the leader in question and therefore leadership is the leader and his team performing to deliver better services to the people in the community. As depicted by one of the respondents.

Leadership in the health context is having a recognised channel or team with someone to spearhead them with a purpose for the common goal (Personal communication with a clinical officer at Dzaipi health centre III, October 2016)

“Leadership to me is when you as a leader in the health sector, oversees the operation and organization of the health institution; you are the head and you need to guide them (team of health staffs), help and monitor what others under you do” (Personal communication with a clinical officer at Pakelle H/C III, Nov 2016)

Leadership is working as a team, a team in which others are entrusted with guiding and leading others to attain a health objective, leaders give tasks to others and others obey by obliging to do the tasks assigned in order to achieve organizational goals. (Personal communication with a clinical officer a midwife at Kococa H/C III, October 2016)

Leadership is a multi-tasking responsibility to leaders in the health institutions within the local government parameters; leadership also comes with effective coordination of departmental activities with the health institutions. Some respondents interviewed attached leadership to numerous tasks of administration health institution that results to effective health service delivery.

the study clearly reveals that a relatively fair number of respondents understood what leadership is and what is expected of leadership in the health sector, more especially at the health centre IIIs; there was a link between leadership and leader, without a leader there is nothing like leadership,

in the health sector where the life of the majority of people depend effective leadership and maternal health service delivery. There is need to have a vibrant and effective leadership in place to influence and inspire towards effective maternal health service delivery in the health sector.

4.2.1.2 Women leadership

In this research, it was vital to tackle the issues of women leadership, to look at it from the perspective of the respondents what their understanding of women leadership was and whether they attribute well to the women leadership; in the study most of the respondents were able to identify with women leadership and asserted that women leadership is very key for the success of health departments such as maternal and child health departments at the health centres III level in the sub counties. Some respondents relate women leadership to the nature and role assigned to them by the creator, tidiness/cleanliness and the fact that the health sector is a perfect fit to manifest or put to use such God given talents to the benefit of many in the community but not only confined at home.

“Women are capable, influential, exemplary and honest in whatever assignments given and are also efficient” (personal communication with a senior clinical officer at Openzinzi H/C III, October 2016)

If you consider the percentage of women in the health sector, the nurses are the biggest and very key for the delivery of health services, most of the activities in the health sector are hands on, most of the drugs prescribed must be administered or monitored; so women play a very big role in health service delivery and participate a lot in health activities, I can boldly say that women are capable of leadership in the health sector” (personal communication with a clinical officer at Pakelle H/C III, October 2016)

The issue of women leadership in the health sector was linked with the question of capability as seen above, regardless of the sex/gender of the leader, so long as the leadership is effective and efficient in delivering services to the community/public, there is no need for alarm, and most respondents believe that women if given the platform can outperform their male counterparts in delivering services to the community, however, there are issues raised about the outburst of their emotions in public which sometimes brings their leadership in questions and also the transfer of socks from home to staffs and eventually on patients which sometimes brings in bad reports about

their leadership but regardless of some these few issues, women leadership is effective in service delivering in the health sector.

4.2.1.3 Maternal health

Understanding the concept of maternal health is vital to this study, and more so from the view of the respondents, and majority of the responses based on the data collected, referred to maternal health as the health of the mother and the child right from the time of conception to the period after delivery of the child(post-natal period)

Maternal health encompasses a lot of thing, it entails a holistic approach to the health of the mother and the child, from the spiritual, economical and psychosocial making the mother sound in all aspects, you can't talk of the health in terms of the services provided alone but also the economic part of it. Because if a mother is poor she cannot afford to some of the basic requirements of for maternity (ANC) to meet the minimum requirements for a mother to deliver safely in a given health centre, if a mother is poor, you cannot say the mother is healthy, therefore looking at the economic bit of it is very important because the health of mother is important we all come from mothers, helping to boost their economic status is very key and important, the man can't leave alone without a woman neither female without a male, eve was created for Adam, and therefore eve is key for the success of Adam, we need mothers to be healthy for our community to thrive, if not we shall register the downfall of the human race”(personal communication with a clinical officer at pakelle h/c III, October 2016)

Maternal health concerns mothers and children, it therefore refers to how to care for a pregnant mother from pregnancy to the postnatal periods, it is basically caring for mothers and their children” (personal communication with a nursing officer (in charge) at Pachara h/c III, October 2016)

“Maternal health refers to the wellbeing of women in their child bearing age” (personal communication with the CAO at adjumani district headquarters, November 2016)

Maternal health refers to health and wellbeing of a pregnant women. According to some respondents, maternal health relates to the health of both the mother and her child, which is very critical for the safety of both. Therefore, there is need to avail all maternal health services for the mothers right from the time when she has conceived to the time after her baby is perfectly safe

4.2.1.4 Communication

This research investigated the aspect of communication and communication strategies in place at the different health centre III facilities under male leadership and female leadership, to draw an impact implication at the way leaders communicate to both clients and staff at the health facility and how it impacts on maternal health outcomes at the facility. Under which the research was able to focus on four core relationship aspects of communication in the health sector as explained below:

4.2.1.4.1 Client-service provider relationship

Basing on the responses from respondents during interviews and focus group discussions, most respondents of this study agreed and emphasised the importance of communication between a client (service user) and health worker (service provider) because the first point of contact when patients come to health facilities seeking treatments is between the health workers and the patients, so communication between the patient and health workers is very key in the image it creates about the service provided in a given health facility and its staff. Most of the health in charges and the health workers interviewed reported that their client-service provider communication is very good and for that reason they are able to attract more clients at their health facilities.

4.2.1.4.2 Interpersonal relationship

Most respondents believe that working in an health facility like H/C III requires a person to have a good interpersonal relationship with the people he/she is trying to serve and also be able to communicate with them freely and create rapport between himself/herself and the clients, it also applies to the in charge at the health facility, interpersonal skills in communication are necessary for effectively manage an H/C facility well.

The health facility in-charge workers relationship is also important for effective health service delivery; the in charge should be able to relate well with his fellow workers and communicate for effectiveness in service delivery at the health centre.

The study revealed that women in charges relate well with fellow workers in the health facility they head, a midst challenges they experience in their work as head of facility; challenges from within and without the health setting; men heading health facilities also are reported to relate well with people but sometime most men seem to be rigid and strict with their fellow staffs; but this

also brings in the question of personality and character of the in charge which can affect performance of worker at the health facility.

4.2.1.4.3 Feedback mechanism

Almost all the interviewed in charges and health workers acknowledged having a feedback mechanism at health facility of how they get feedback from the community about the services they are offering and the level of satisfaction clients are getting from the facility:

All the health in-charges interviewed noted the village health team as an important feedback mechanism to the health facility; through the village health team, they get to know what is happening in the community by receiving their complains and addressing them after getting them from the VHTs

“Engaging the VHTs seems to be the most effective way of getting feedback from the community because the VHT are part of the community and therefore can interact freely with the grass root people and be able to lodge their complains” (Personal communication with a senior clinical medical officer at openzinzi H/C III, October 2016)

Another identified mechanism is community dialogue between the community and the health workers of a given health facility; having a community dialogue meetings at the local levels and issues raised in such meetings are forwarded to the health unit to be improved on or avoided.

The health unit management committee also plays an important role in getting feedbacks from public, through HUMC identified complains can be forwarded, discussed and worked on, success celebrated by all staffs of the health unit; therefore HUMC is a very important component because it comprises of the local people and health workers at the health facility.

“it is easier to get feedback from the community for instance when we sit for management committee which comprises of people from the community, in case of complains, it can easily be addressed, we have the local council one and teachers as part of the committee (HUMC)” (personal communication a nursing officers (in charge) at Arinyapi H/C III, October 2016) .

Suggestion box is also feedback mechanism mentioned by some respondents of the study, a box where clients can put their grudges after writing them on a piece of paper. They are only few H/C III facilities that has a suggestion box in place; and others relates to the illiteracy level of the

community to justify themselves of not having a suggestion box, yet others who have noted a positive response from the community.

Having connections within the community was also noted by some respondents as a better way of getting feedback directly from the community, from friends you can get to know what is happening and what people are saying about your leadership and services offered in the community at the health facility.

“I have friends, I ask them about our work and performance; for instance I asked the LC III last time about our work and how we are performing at the health centre, he said that people in the community are atleast saying there is a difference in service delivered at the health facility and the community members wish me to stay and not be transferred” (personal communication with a nursing officers at Pachara H/C III, October 2016)

4.2.1.4.4 Communication strategies

Communication strategies are important in any organization/institution; there is need to have a clear way of communicating to people in a given institution; many respondents interviewed revealed that communication is important and below are the strategies identified in the course of the interview

Health education is one communication strategy used in H/C III facilities to communicate to clients seeking maternity services and other health related services at the health facility. All respondents interviewed acknowledged health education as a strategy in place and being implemented at the health facility/unit.

“What we do is try to make our clients aware of the services we offer, we give health education at outpatient department, before we see our patients, somebody talks to them in groups and individuals, we ask them a few questions, how they feel about our services” (personal communication a clinical officer at Ukusijoni H/C III, October 2016)

One way of communicating to clients is through the use of community linkage health officers (VHT), they are given the necessary and useful information to communicate to the people in the villages within the catchment areas of the health facility/unit.

Respondents also mentioned community outreaches as another way of communicating to the community about services offered by the health unit; community outreaches bring services consumers and services providers face to face, questions are asked and answers given to the community.

The use of phones in communication was mentioned by a few respondents as being used for communicating to mothers; for instance some health facility have a phone for the facility; for contacting mothers from home and reminding them of their appointment before it is due.

Another way of communicating identified, is the use of the church platform, this strategy was sighted by health facilities that are mission based or managed by the Catholic Church.

“Another way of enabling the communities to communicate to us through the church, it is the simplest way of communicating about the services offered at the health facility and whatever is done at the health unit” (personal communication a nursing officers a clinical officer at adjumani H/C III, October 2016)

4.2.1.4.5 In charge-workers relationship

Most of the respondents in the health workers category, reported to have good relationship to their in charges, this good relationship does not depend on the gender or sex of the in charges but rather a mutual relationship that aims at building trust among themselves as people working for the common good of the people in the community to which they are to serve.

4.2.2 Maternal health facility status

The status of the maternity facility is crucial to depict the type of leadership and nature of services offered, based on the observation guide and interview with in-charges and health and health workers; the following issues were highlighted during

4.2.2.1 Maternity ward capacity and status

All the health facility IIIs, have a maternity wards, but the capacity and status are variety; there are 16 health centre IIIs in Adjumani district, 2 are NGO administered, 3 are run by mission and 11 are government health facilities.

The maternity ward status of the health facility III involved under this research are fairly good with exception of a few cases, where the maternity status are very poor and for that reason, have

to shift to the general ward; the maternity ward under the mission headed health centre are in good condition and well maintained; one of the mission headed H/C III has a newly constructed maternity wing; with all the requirements, the other 2 are in old structure but well maintained; all these facilities are headed by women. The two NGO health facility IIIs are in good conditions well equipped to address the needs of the refugee community but also accessible by the host communities. The other eleven health facilities are local government facilities; the status of those health facilities are in poor state apart from a few facilities where other implementing partners(IPs) have an hand in their operation and has managed to construct maternity wings in some of the health facilities owned by the government but the rest of the health centre three facilities are in bad shapes and in some cases none existence of maternity wards, they instead resort to using the general ward to rest mothers after delivery.

Majority of the government facilities have 5 beds in the maternity ward for postnatal recoveries and resting and one delivery bed for delivery during labour. the capacity of the maternity of most of the facility is 8 beds with one delivery bed, there are only two facilities of the sixteen that has two delivery beds; most beds in the government facilities are old; a total of 5 health facilities attach mosquito nets to the beds for mothers, the rest instruct mothers to come with their nets during labour times.

4.2.2.2 Availability of placenta pit

In observation, all the 16 health centre IIIs have placenta pits, most of the placenta pits are in bad shape, some have cracked and stinking and for others they are in bush y environment not well maintained and some do not have ventilation, not fenced or protected; of the 16 health facilities, 4 health centres have fenced placenta pit, slashed environment but he rest of the remaining placenta pit are not fenced, are in the bush and in bad shape

4.2.2.3 Sanitation

In term of sanitation, the entire health centre III sanitation is good; there have rubbish pits, dustbins placed within the facility, accessible by clients who come for treatment at the health facility; the status of the toilets and the bathrooms are good, with exception of 3 governments headed health centre where the toilets and bathrooms are in bad shapes and atleast 70% of the toilets and bathrooms are in good shapes but the rest needs to be attended to; and some of the health facilities

don't have toilets or bathrooms for mothers, they have to use general toilets and bathrooms to help themselves.

4.2.3 Maternity workforce

Effectiveness and efficiency in health service delivery requires a proficient workforce with all the training necessary to execute their health responsibilities to the public; here the nature of the workforce at the health centre is explored and gaps identified for correction

4.2.3.1 Categorisation of workforce at the health centre

All the health centres have these staffs: senior clinical officer; clinical officer; registered nurse; enrolled nurse; midwives, both registered and enrolled midwives; accountant for most mission headed health centres; record assistant; laboratory technician and assistant; nursing assistant, health assistant, porters and security guard.

Most government headed facilities have health workers in between 14-18 in numbers of staffs and other mission headed facilities and NGO managed facilities have staffs within 10-14 in numbers.

4.2.3.2 Professional regulations/code of conduct

Basing on the responses from respondents, most admitted to have professional regulations from the ministry; the medical code of conduct for medical profession, and also noted that during appointments to service, the district outlines what is expected of the worker being employed into the health sector

Many H/C III in charges, also noted that in addition to the medical code of conduct, appointments from the district, also lays regulations to do; they also have formulated internal rules for health workers at the facility to abide by, failure to abide by those rules formulated, one will have to appear before the disciplinary of the health centre.

4.2.3.3 Motivation and professional development

4.2.3.3.1 Motivation

The concept of motivation is very important in better health service delivery; it is people who work in the health centres and there is need to encourage these people to work hard for better health service delivery; basing on the respondents responses during interview, they emphasised the

importance of motivation in the health sector for workers; and many respondents admitted to having motivation strategies in place to encourage their workers for better performance

the word of thank given to a staff who has performed his/her duty diligently is enough to motivate that worker to do more better; therefore appreciation is key to the performance of health staffs at the health centre.

Another way of motivating workers cited during the interviews was delegation of responsibilities to staffs in specific departments at the health centre; motivates them to perform and deliver better services because, they are total accountable to the in-charge after responsibility has been delegated.

Some respondents noted the issue of internal supervision of workers is also another way of motivating workers to perform better.

“We have internal supervision as a motivation tool, we move around the wards to supervise staffs on duties which also encourage them to perform better services” (personal communication with a clinical officer at adjumani mission H/C III, October 2016)

Respondents also cited workers appraisal as another way of motivating them; by appraising them well, you encourage them to perform better in their duties.

“When you are doing workers appraisal you have to appraise them; in the appraisal meetings, you have to atleast write something that can motivate someone; when workers do what is expected of them, you appraise them, it will motivate them” (personal communication with a nursing officer at Arinyapi H/C III, October 2016)

The only available monetary motivation pointed by many respondents in the PHC funds given to the health facilities, once received by the health facility ; it is given to workers in forms of allowances to motivate them in the work they do. Many cited rotational outreaches in the community, so that all staffs can benefit from this fund PHC and be motivated.

In addition to the above in case of workshop; staffs are also rotated, not the same staffs every time there is a workshop but one have to appoint different staffs to attend at different times of workshop so as to be motivated to work and be committed to serving the public.

Recognition of a best performer during meetings, was noted as a way of motivating staffs during the interviews, this act encourages others to also strive to do better so as to recognised and appreciated

“In meeting we reward best performers by recognition; by clapping to them and this way they are motivated” **(personal communication with a clinical officer at pakelle H/C III, October 2016)**

Organising for staff welfare is also a way of motivating health workers to perform better in health service delivery.

“When money comes, we organise staff farewell, the staffs decide what to buy with the money” **(personal communication with a nursing officers at pachara H/C III, October 2016)**

4.2.3.3.2 Professional development

Basing on the interviews with health in-charges and health workers, the issue of professional development was a matter of choice or interest to the person who waits to advance in his/her profession; however many respondents cited to have encouraged their workers to pursue professional development because the health field is dynamic, knowledge already acquired can become obsolete, if one does not progress with professional advancement.

“Health is dynamic, if you do not keep updated in the near future your knowledge would be obsolete and you start behaving like a witch doctor; if you don’t go for professional development; like here we have CMEs (updates of knowledge) if someone wants to upgrade to another level we accept that and write to the district and the district allows the person to upgrade” (Personal communication with a clinical officer at pakelle H/C III, October 2016)

Apart from advising workers to pursue professional development, most facilities have no clear programs in place for professional development of staffs.

4.2.4 Maternal health services at health facilities

It’s relevant to know that maternal health services packages offered at the health facilities for clients, more especially mothers seeking maternity services at these health facilities:

4.2.4.1 Facility based delivery

All of the facilities involved in this study; more so health centre III conduct facility based delivery for mothers within their catchment areas, in cases of complications referrals are made to the health centre IV or to the hospital

4.2.4.2 Antenatal care (ANC)

In regards to the interview conducted and observation made, all health centres III involved in this research have antenatal care for mothers who are pregnant

4.2.4.3 Postnatal care

All health facilities, provides post-natal care services for mothers after delivery at the health facility.

Most of the health facilities do follow ups, holistic check-ups after delivery; testing mothers for HIV after six weeks; health education, supplementary and complementary feeding for children; clinical assessments done for children in most health facilities level IIIs in the district.

4.2.4.4 Family planning services

Family planning services are offered in most health centre III, except for the three catholic mission managed health centres that don't conduct health facility except for natural family planning which may be tricky for many couples who come for family planning but these health centres do not administer artificial family planning, simply because the family planning philosophy is not in line with the catholic faith.

4.2.4.5 Immunization

Child immunization is offered in all the health centres III, involved in the study, most respondents noted that mothers bring their children on appointments

4.2.5 Quality of maternity care

4.2.5.1 Effectiveness

In terms of effectiveness, most respondents during interviews accepted that, most if not all mothers who attended their maternal survives from antenatal care services; delivery and post-natal services receive appropriate care from the health workers at the health facility

4.2.5.2 Safety

In terms of the incidence of outcomes for maternal deaths and infant mortality at the health centre IIIs most facilities referred to their facilities as safe for deliveries, because most facilities reported to have never registered deaths apart from still births, in case of complications, referrals are made to higher health facility levels like health IV or the hospital for this reason the incidence of occurrence for deaths is zero for most health facilities.

4.2.5.3 Efficiency

Most health facilities, maternal health services packages provides the value for money according to most respondents because all the expected packages are being delivered to clients and based on the resources received at the health centres the outputs are relatively fine

4.2.6 Maternal health care-consumer satisfaction

4.2.6.1 Personal expectations

Most health facilities headed by women admitted to meeting the personal expectations of mothers who come to these health facilities; however, some respondents honestly argued that you can't meet all personal expectations of women who come to the health facility because some expectations are weird.

“We cannot all meet the expectations of women who come for maternity services, some of the expectations of these mothers are weird; we only meet the minimum expectations which is to give them safe delivery; some of the weird expectations of mothers include; mothers expect midwives to stay by their side all the time which is impossible, but we give them mama kits, our time; sometime mothers come late and expect to be attended first even in the absence of staffs at the facility; and some tend to migrate to other health centres” (Person communication with the in charge of pakelle health centre III, October 2016)

While the situation seems different in female headed health facilities, most of the female headed facilities noted meeting the expectations of mothers, when they come for maternity services

“Most of our mothers are in contact with the midwives, their expectations are met as soon as they arrive; they are attended to and go home on time and happily, I normally see that on their faces, and meeting their expectations depends on what services they have come for and they do not go

back without meeting their needs” (Pers. comm. with an enrolled nurse at Robidire H/C III, October 201)

4.2.6.2 Time and support to clients

In line with the interviews, most respondents admitted to giving enough time and support to mothers during ANC, delivery and postnatal periods to ensure the safety of both mother and the child.

“We do not have any fixed time for mothers, but we try to help them, as much, as soon, as quick, as possible” (Pers. comm. with enrolled nurse at Robidire H/C III, October 2016)

“We give mothers as much time as is enough but sometimes it depends on schedule and business” (Pers. comm. with a midwife at Maryland Kocoa H/C III, October 2016)

Most respondents revealed that they give mothers enough time and support during their pregnancy; timeframe of 15 minutes to 20 minutes is given to mothers who come to seek for maternity services in the health facilities.

4.3 attitudes and perceptions on leadership in the health sector

The attitudes and perceptions of people to women leadership is very important it depicts how people respond to the leadership of women in the health sector.

Most respondents in this research study expressed positive attitudes toward women leadership in the health sector and believed that women can deliver and even outperform their male counterparts in service delivery; many also said that opportunities for leadership should be given to women by training them for service delivery in the community

“Women are performing well as leaders, good and capable, it is not women leading women but a position taken up by a woman to influence other people who she is leading to achieve a particular goal” (Pers. comm. with a medical laboratory technician at Maryland Kocoa H/C III, October 2016)

Other respondents acknowledged that women leadership is vital not only in the health sector but also in other social institutions, and deliver better outputs at all the levels of their involvement;

others also believe that women leaders are transparent and accountable compared to men leadership

Transparent, have good relationship, have kind heart and also women in the family follow up with her children' education and better lives for the children, it is important for women to undertake leadership” **(Pers. comm. with an enrolled nurse at Robidire H/C III, October 2016)**

“ women leadership results to better service delivery in the health sector, it is crucial to have best talented people regardless their sex working toward achieving health objectives in the health sector” **(Pers. comm. with an enrolled midwife at Robidire H/C III, October 2016)**

Some respondents believe that women are cable of leadership but their leadership is hindered by a lot of factors that also affects their performance in the health sector. “ women are capable in leadership, though in leadership, they cannot perform as men, in comparing the two, you can see a lot of variation, for instance men are short tempered and men normally give command in delivery, but women are emotional and cannot handle like men” **((Pers. comm. with an enrolled midwife at Robidire H/C III, October 2016))**

4.4 challenges in the health leadership

One challenge that is evidently affecting women in leadership; is that most women leaders who are approachable are in the “elite capture” this makes interaction between women leaders and women at local levels very poor because this leaders can only be approached by those of her class not the poor woman or mother in the village who knows nothing about classes and education.

This is also an issue of low self-esteem among women leaders, women leaders are sometimes scared of the male community around them and for this reason can't present themselves well before superiors and bosses who are men

Another challenge women leadership faces in the issue of unenlightened men, who are resistant and adamant in allowing their women to take up leadership position and deliver services to the community or general public.

In addition to that is the issue of innovativeness and creativity most lack those skills of being innovative and creative and because of these hindrance, most health in charges do not deliver to the expectations.

When it comes to the general management of facilities; women have problems of their own, their husbands demand their presence at home, absenteeism, child rearing and family issues distract female employees in their performance.

The other issue also raised in this study in line with women leadership is the issue of emotional outburst, women are prone to expressing their emotions even in public, and this somehow reveals their vulnerability and a loophole in administration.

Poor male involvement under women leadership was also noted as a challenge women leadership face. Male are scantily involved when women are leaders; however, it is not always the case, because some respondents reported to have no problem with male involvement in health activities under women leadership

Male chauvinism, male think they are natural leaders and for this wrongly misplaced belief. They do not respect women leaders who are positioned to lead them in the health sector.

Some women also lack confidence in themselves. This can be attributed to cultural issues or factors where they believe that men are supposed to be leaders but not women.

4.5 leadership and decision making at the health sector

This section explains how leadership can influence decision making for mothers to make and take up good decisions for their health and the health of their child, and also explores how these women are involved in decision making during maternity seeking times in their pregnancy

4.5.1 Women involvement in decision making

In relation to the responses from respondents during interviews, many revealed that women involvement in decision making concerning their health is significant because it is her health and she has to make choices that can better meet her interests; however, there are only a few cases, where respondents believed that women or mothers should be allowed to decide, more so concerning drugs prescribed by physicians, because many of them are in the business of not taking drugs and harbouring wrong perceptions about drugs given the mothers i.e. the iron platelets given to increase blood in mothers

“We at this health facility allow women to make decision for themselves, she is an adult, no one can come and decide for herself what is appropriate for her health” (an interview with a clinical officer)

“During consultation you give her time to explain herself, after asking a few questions; and you explain to her the state of her condition and prescribe drugs for her, which she must take” ((**Pers. comm. with a nursing officer at Robidire H/C III, October 2016**))

According to the respondents I interviewed, they allow pregnant women and mothers to make decision but in case of wrong decision, an interactive session is initiated to change the attitude of the mother concerning the decision she has taken. Also some respondents noted that mothers are allowed to make decisions for them, like some mothers decide to only see a staff throughout their pregnancy. Therefore there is a variation the extent and degree of allowing mothers and pregnant mothers make decision, it can and also depend on the nature of decision she has to make.

4.5.2 Women leadership, planning and maternal health

The highest planning organ in the district is the district council that is responsible for the formulation of policy and approvals of plans, budgets and work plans; the district council has women elected by the public that can influence the process for their interests, the standing committees also have women members who can influence policy and decision at the district and lower local governments, even during implementation of plans, women are brought on board; maternal sector is the best place to involve women in.

The majority of the respondents cited that planning and involvement of women for maternal health services, is based on a bottom up planning strategy. This is where health centre facilities headed by nurses undertake their planning at that level before submission is made to the district health departments; but even as the facilities carry their planning, they have to incorporate the health needs of the communities before a final submission to the district. At the district a participatory planning is conducted by the district, whereby all facilities head are invited to attend and other key stakeholders, after which plans are subsisted to the district council for approvals before execution or implementation of the activates are done.

The planning strategy involves all people or key stakeholders. This ensures that women are also part of the planning process at all levels right from the bottom to the top, this way all their needs and interest are part of the plans that submitted for council approval.

4.5.3 Women representation in the health sector

There is a fair representation of women in the health department at the district levels, the council also has women elected to represent women interests and voice in the district councils, many workers in the health sector are women; currently the assisted DHO for maternal child health is a woman who is also the health officer in the district; EPI is also headed by a woman, the principal nursing officer of the hospital is a woman, the child health department is headed by a woman; antenatal is also headed by a woman, there is fair representation of women in the health departments at the district.

4.5.4 Institutional support and access to leadership in the health sector

The health departments conducts Capacity building in governance, leadership and management, where trainings are done and follow-ups are made for the people trained, based on these assigned duties. Effective responsibilities are given to health workers.

Technical supervision with mentorship or coaching is emphasised with the health sector, this encourages people to pursue quality care in the health sector and also see from others what is being done with effectiveness and therefore deliver better services in the health sector.

Most key informants, pointed at the good political relationship between women leaders and the politicians at the district and this motivates women to deliver health services to the general public, good political relationship ensure efficiency in health service delivery at the health centres. This is the reason politicians are sent to the offices in the district.

“When leaders talk, they talk with authority, because they are elected, and people respond well to elected leaders. They create good relationship for effective service delivery in the health sector”
(Pers. comm. With a CAO at adjumani district headquarters, October 2016)

4.6 Discussion of findings

The findings presented in the preceding paragraphs have connections with scholarly work linked to women leadership, not only in the health sector but also in other sector; and most agree that

leadership is key for effective service delivery in the community. Without effective leadership in any social institution, health service delivery would be a dream to be dreamed and remembered but not effected to the benefit of the entire community. Maternal health service delivery needs leadership that has lived the talk and can articulate the interest of women to authorities concerned without fear and compromise.

The success of the health service delivery in terms of its effectiveness, safety and efficiency depends on the leadership of the health centre/sector without leadership, service delivery in the health sector, more so, effective service delivery and performance cannot be achieved. Therefore leadership is very important for an improved service delivery in maternal services.

Majority of the health centres under women leadership are performing well in maternal health service delivery. They are managing their infrastructure and staffs well and that has helped encouraged and motivated their workers to work and deliver service to the clients who come for health service at the given health facility. The general cleanliness and sanitation of women headed facilities are generally good and sanitation is well observed, because women pay attention to details and strive for cleanness. Maternal issues is a woman issue. This should be at the fore play of the mind-set of people, but better maternal health outcomes can't be attained without the involvement of many stakeholders in the delivery of maternal health services in the health sector.

Women leaders can use their position, as leaders to push for the general interest of women because they are better positioned to articulate the interests of women to higher authorities, and act as a voice to the many rural poor women who cannot raise their voices in offices and at health service delivery points in case of any dissatisfaction their get from health service providers

According to Michael west et al (2015), effective leaders in health services emphasis continually safe, high quality and compassionate care as top priority. They ensure that the voice of patients is consistently heard at every level, patient experience, concerns, needs and feedback (positive and negative) are consistently attended to. They offer supportive, available, empathic, fair, respectful, compassionate and empowering leadership. They promote participation and involvement as their core leadership strategy. They ensure the staff 'voice' is encouraged, heard and acted on across the organization and provide practical support for staff to innovate within safe boundaries.

The research also agree with some scholars that effective leaders in the health sector ensure everyone is clear about what they are required to do and give helpful, positive feedback on performance, including appreciation. They insist on transparency in relation to errors, serious incidents, complaints and problems and they regard mistakes as opportunities for learning. They act effectively to deal with poor performance and proactively address aggressive, inappropriate and unacceptable behaviors displayed by staff or patients/carers.

As stated by Michael west et al (2015); this research agrees with them in that effective leaders promote continuous development of the knowledge, skills and abilities of staff in order to improve quality of patient care, safety, compassion and the patient experience. They consistently encourage, motivate and reward innovation and introduce new and improved ways of working.

This research reveals that maternal health services can be improved as a result of women leadership in the health sector, women leaders are able and willing to involve and engage stakeholders in services delivery and many of women leaders are open to suggestions and critics; on which they make improvement on service delivered, a reflection of the leadership context.

Majority of the health workforce are women, mostly in the nursing cadre and women are positioned to head the maternal child health department at the district headquarters, is a clear reflection of their capabilities in dealing with issues related to maternal health; better performers when it comes to maternal health services in the health sector.

The research also comes to an agreement with most literature on leadership and health care, that majority of the health workers are women, but only a small percent of these women take up the leadership roles in the health sector. According to this research only 45 % of women take up leadership in health centres, this may be because they are not given opportunities to lead in the health setting; education wise, most women do not think of upgrading once they have achieved their first qualifications, however with the experiences they have in the health sector, they can be entrusted to lead in the health settings.

Women are better positioned to communicate and guard their fellow women in issues related to maternal health. These are people who have lived the talk, they know what it means to be a mother, good and great sympathizers, who can act quickly to the needs of the women seeking maternal health services at the respective health facilities. All these encourages mothers to seek maternal

health services at health centre facilities that are headed by women compared to those headed by male counterparts. Although most women in the focus group aligned themselves well with male health workers compared to female health workers who are sometimes harsh on them and cruel, so many mothers prefer to be attended by men who are friendly to them.

In a study carried by Dawson et al (2011), reveals that where health service staff report they are well-led and have high levels of satisfaction with their immediate supervisors, patients report that they, in turn, are treated with respect, care and compassion (Dawson et al, 2011). Overall, the information suggests that when health care staff feels their work climate is positive and supportive, as evidenced by coherent, integrated and supportive people management practices. There are low and declining levels of patient mortality. These associations are consistent across all the domains of health care - acute, mental health, primary care and ambulance. Engagement also appears to be higher in health care organisations where leaders create a positive climate for staff so they feel involved and have the emotional capacity to care for others. (Dawson et al., 2011)

This research also agrees that team work is an important contributor to health care quality. Leaders must ensure that health care staff work together across professional boundaries to deliver high quality care, particularly as the complexity of health care increases and co-morbidity becomes more common (West & Lyubovnikova, 2012; West, 2012).

CHAPTER 5

5.0 Conclusions and recommendations

This chapter presents conclusions and recommendations or suggestions by the researcher basing on the study findings and according to the study objectives.

5.1 Conclusions

5.1.1 The role of women leadership in promoting maternal health services.

Women leadership has influenced maternal health service outcomes in many ways, and it has resulted into better performance of health services in the different health centres in the district, as revealed in the research that most health facilities headed by women perform better because women who become in charges are trained to handle issues to related mothers and child health. Therefore by increasing women leadership in the health sector, better services will be delivered to the community in line with maternal health services.

Most of the performance of the leadership depends on their traits and personality, therefore women leaders, given the character god has given them to be mothers and kind hearts can perform and deliver services.

5.1.2 The attitudes and perceptions of maternal health service users (clients) on women leadership in the health sector

There different and various attitudes and perceptions of maternal health services users and other people on women leadership, others believe that women are not capable of doing things men do and others think women can if given the opportunity to leader and guides in the health sector, as evidenced by the research done; most health facilities headed by women are performing well in line with the maternal health services delivery and service users has reported satisfaction from health facility headed by women more often compared to those headed by men. Almost 80% of maternal health services users assert that women leadership in the health sector is very important for that success of maternal health service delivery.

Attitudes and perceptions on women as leaders in the health sector may be different, but at a given point all believe that women are capable leaders in the health sector and if right initiatives are in place and opportunities given they can deliver and make the health sector a better place then what

we can see; therefore there is a positive attitudes towards women being leaders in the health sector by service users and other people interviewed during the process of data collection.

5.1.3 Barriers and constrains that affects women leadership and Measures to overcome them.

There are a number of relatively well-identified practical strategies that can be taken to develop cultures of high quality, safe and compassionate patient care. Leadership is the most influential factor in shaping organisational culture, so ensuring the necessary leadership strategies, behaviours and qualities are developed is fundamental to health service improvement. The key questions must focus on: what does the research evidence reveal about leaders' behaviours, leadership more generally and outcomes in health care.

The main challenge faced in the health sector is to nurture cultures that ensure the delivery of continuously improving high quality, safe and compassionate care. Leadership is the most influential factor in shaping organizational culture so ensuring the necessary leadership behaviours, strategies and qualities are developed is fundamental. There is clear evidence of the link between leadership and a range of important outcomes within health services, including patient satisfaction, patient mortality, organizational financial performance, staff well-being, engagement, turnover and absenteeism, and overall quality of care.

The challenges that face health sectors are too great and too many for leadership to be left to chance, to fads and fashions or to piecemeal approaches. This review suggests that approaches to developing leaders, leadership and leadership strategy can and should be based on robust theory with strong empirical support and evidence of what works in health care. Health care organisations can confidently face the future and deliver the high quality, compassionate care that is their mission by developing and implementing leadership strategies that will deliver the cultures they require to meet the health care needs of the populations they serve.

5.1.4 Women leadership and decision making

Women in leadership are given the mandate to make decisions in the interest of the common good and the public, this is a clear indication that once women are in leadership positions they make decisions that affects the entire public and they are capable of making; to add on to that women headed facilities often give more chances to women to make decisions and decide concerning their

health and the health of their children when it comes to choosing were to deliver and were to take their children for immunization. Leadership in the health sector goes with decision making in line with allocation of resources to meet the needs of the health sector and the service users.

5.2 Recommendations

Supporting women's collective action; the evidence is unequivocal that women organizing with other women are instrumental to their politicisation and solidarity, as well as for their ability to exert the collective power and influence necessary to shift entrenched legal and social norms that marginalize women. Health Institutions that are often successful are those that start by addressing the immediate and practical concerns of women, which then supports addressing longer-term strategic goals in the health sector. Caution needs to be taken not to essentialise women and their interests and to allow local women to drive their own causes

Women's organizations with established relationships with grassroots women's groups are essential to develop poorer women's leadership and mobilization capabilities. As importantly, strong links between professional and grassroots organisation ensures the everyday needs and concerns of poor women informs national advocacy by elite women, and connects community action to broader socio-political movements. Women need also to build coalitions and networks with decision-makers and other stakeholders in a strong position to advance women's empowerment through appropriate political, economic and social strategies, including, for example, ministries of finance, the private sector, and the NGO community.

Designing and implementing social accountability (and any other) interventions in ways that increase both their sustainability and empowerment impact; This includes inputs to address the specific barriers women, and particularly poor and marginalised women, face to meaningful participation, such as holding meetings at appropriate times and places, providing childcare, and facilitating women-only discussions or groups. It also involves efforts to make bounded accountability interventions relevant to the, often more practical, concerns of women while embedding them in broader social movements to encourage women's ongoing conscientisation and influence.

In all areas, engaging with men and with key political actors with decision-making power is central to strategies to improve decision-making, voice and influence. Women's 'triple burden' of responsibility for unpaid domestic work, reproduction and childcare in addition to any paid work is a fundamental constraint on their participation in political and civic life. Changing this requires working with both women and men to change social and cultural ideas about 'masculine norms', including the division of labour, and providing targeted services, such as quality childcare services or improved infrastructure to reduce the time women must spend on domestic activities.

5.3 Areas for further research

There is need to carry further research in the following areas, as raised by some respondents during data collection.

1. The impact of domestic violence on the health of pregnant women in Uganda.
2. Effect of health and nutrition programme on Antenatal care attendance in adjumani district.
3. Strategies to promote women leadership in the health sector.
4. Non-government organization and maternal health service delivery in adjumani district

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